

STUDY OF SCHEMES OF VARYING COMPLEXITY IN THE MULTISIM PROGRAM

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Abstract. In the process of modeling electronic devices on the computer, the acquired theoretical knowledge is consolidated through laboratory and practical classes. However, in most of these classes, due to the insufficient number of laboratory benches, as well as the lack of modern instruments and devices, we cannot always achieve the expected result. A virtual laboratory is a software package that allows users to acquire skills in working with various devices and systems and to study them comprehensively. One such program that provides students with such opportunities is Multisim. In Multisim program it is possible to study circuits of various degrees of complexity, design, simulate and study analog and digital radio-electronic devices of any complexity. In the experimental circuit below, a single stage AC amplifier on an n-p-n bipolar transistor with common emitter is considered.

Keywords: amplifier, transistor, separating capacitor, function generator, gain, signal harmonics, chokes.

Introduction

One of the software tools for modeling electronic devices is Multisim program. In Multisim it is possible to study circuits of different complexity. In this case, let's consider the circuit of an amplifier on a bipolar transistor.

In the amplifier it is important to study the types of DC stabilization and tuning modes, to understand the purpose of elements in amplifier circuits, as well as to obtain information about the frequency characteristics of the parameters of amplifier stages. These aspects are important in the study of electronics.

The experimental circuit below (Fig. 1) shows a single stage AC amplifier on an n-p-n bipolar common emitter transistor.

Fig-1. Schematic diagram of a single stage common emitter AC amplifier

MAIN PART

The purpose of the elements of the circuit is as follows:

- Q1 - transistor; serves to convert the DC voltage energy from the source V1 into the amplified signal energy.

- C1 - separating capacitor; separates the input of the stage and the output of the previous stage for DC, and for AC connects them; on the amplitude-frequency response (AFR) causes distortion at low frequencies.

- C2 - blocking capacitor in the emitter circuit of the transistor; eliminates the gain reduction in the operating frequency range, which can occur due to negative feedback created by the element R4; on the AFC also causes distortion at low frequencies.

- R1, R2 are resistors that receive voltage from the source V1; they supply a constant voltage to the base of the transistor, thus providing a collector current corresponding to the operating point. Resistors R1 and R2 determine the input impedance of the stage, the time constant of the low-frequency input signal and the stability of the operating point of the bipolar transistor stage on the DC current.

- R3 - resistor in the collector circuit of the transistor; when the input signal is applied, it changes the collector current and converts it into an output signal; this element is the load of the stage, and its value affects the gain; it also provides a constant voltage between the collector and emitter.

- R4 is a resistor in the emitter circuit; it ensures the stability of the DC operating point of the stage, and finally determines the operating point in the transistor characteristics.

The following measuring instruments are used in the circuit:

- U1 - DC ammeter; measures collector current at the operating point of the transistor.

- U2 - DC voltmeter; used to measure the DC voltage at the emitter of the transistor.

- U3 - DC ammeter; used to measure the base current of the transistor at the operating point.

- XFG1 - function generator; simulates a harmonic input signal source.

- XMM1 - AC voltmeter; used to measure the effective voltage at the output of the XFG1 generator (amplifier input).

- XMM2 - DC or AC voltmeter; measures the voltage across the collector of a transistor or the AC voltage at the output of an amplifier.

- XSC1 - Oscilloscope; allows you to monitor the output waveform.

- XBP1 - Bode analyzer; directly displays the amplitude-frequency response of the circuit on the screen.

This circuit was tested for DC. To do this, the following steps are performed:

The parameters of the working point are determined. The order of the study is as follows: the display window of the generator XFG1 is opened, the minimum value of amplitude (Amplitude) is set at pV; then the display window of the voltmeter XMM2 is opened, which is switched to the DC mode; the power supply of the circuit is turned on, and after some time, when the transients are completed, the power supply is turned off. The readings of the measuring instruments are read. The following results are obtained: - constant collector current; - constant base current; constant collector current constant voltage and emitter voltage, constant voltage having calculated, the data are entered into Table 1

2) The nominal value of the gain is determined.

The nominal AC gain of the amplifier is determined at the middle frequencies with the lowest distortion. In addition, since we have no data on the maximum amplitude of the output signal without distortion, it is necessary to determine the gain at low values of the output voltage. To do this, reduce the input voltage value at the amplifier input in proportion to E_T .

$$K_0 = \frac{U_{\text{ЧНК}}}{E_T}$$

The procedure for measuring output voltages U_{vva} is as follows: open the display windows of voltmeters XMM1 and XMM2 and switch them to AC measurement mode; open the harmonic signal source window of XFG1 and set the frequency (Frequency) to kHz; turn on the circuit power; increase the amplitude of the XFG1 oscillator signal until the amplifier output voltage is $U_v = 100$ mV (this is measured with the XMM2 voltmeter); then turn off the circuit power; calculate the XMM1 voltmeter reading, i.e. measure the amplifier input voltage I_n (also determine the amplitude of the XFG1 oscillator signal).

Table-1.

Parameters	U _{кэ} ^o , V	I _к ^o , mA	I _б ^o , mkA	K ₀	f _н , Hz
experimental					
calculated					—
error, %					—

3) For a cascade assembled on a bipolar transistor, the following calculation formulas are used:

* coordinates of the operating point

$$U_{кэ}^o = E_{\Pi} - U_9^o - I_{к}^o R_3; \quad I_{к}^o = I_9^o - I_б^o; \quad I_б^o \approx I_9^o / (\beta + 1),$$

here $U_9^o \approx E_{\Pi} R_2 / (R_1 + R_2) - U^*$; $I_9^o = U_9^o / R_4$; $U^* \approx 0,6$ B; V1=12 B- V1

Source Voltage;

* Nominal gain value

$$K_0 = -\frac{\alpha R_3}{r^*},$$

here $\alpha = \beta / (1 + \beta)$ – emitter current transfer coefficient;

$r^* = r_3 + r_б(1 - \alpha)$ – input resistance of the common-base circuit

$r_3 \approx 0,025 / I_9^o$ и $r_б \approx 100$ Ом – Small signal parameters of the equivalent circuit of a bipolar transistor.

4) Bode plotter is used to determine the amplitude-frequency and phase-frequency characteristics of the circuit.

Electronic keys are used to switch electrical signals. In low-voltage information devices their role is performed by semiconductor diodes, as well as bipolar and field-effect transistors.

Such devices consist of a key element, control circuitry and energy storage devices. The control circuitry changes the parameters of input pulses on the key element during the control process. Energy storage devices such as chokes and capacitors act as equalizing filters

(demodulators). In contrast to continuously operating stabilizers, pulse voltage stabilizers (PVS) operate in saturation or cut-off mode for a significant part of the cycle, and only during switching operations they are in active mode. That is, when the control transistor is switching, the power dissipation in pulse stabilizers is much less than in continuous stabilizers. Therefore, the utility coefficient (PC) in ICSs is found to be much higher than that of continuous stabilizers over wider ranges of the input voltage. For example, $23B < U_{\text{нст}} < \sqrt{2} \cdot 23B = 34B$ when $U_{\text{юк}} = 20B$ $\eta_{\text{нст}} = 85\%$, $\eta_{\text{юк}} = 55\%$.

The large frequency variations in pulse voltage stabilizers (PVS) result in significant weight and size reductions in transformers and filters.

Disadvantages of pulse voltage stabilizers (PVS) include:

- Significant complexity of the control circuitry;
- High ripple $\Delta U_{\text{юк}}$, radio interference and noise;
- Poor dynamic characteristics.

Depending on the method of output voltage stabilization, there are three types of ICN schemes:

PWM - circuits with frequency-pulse modulation. In these schemes, the duration of pulses at the filter input remains constant, and the intervals between them vary in proportion to the output voltage.

URS - control systems with a relay circuit. In these schemes, the formation of pulses occurs at the moment when the voltage $U_{\text{н}}$ coincides with two horizontal levels: a low level, when the voltage edge is formed, and a high level, when the crossing occurs. The change in the shape of $U_{\text{юк}}$ depending on $U_{\text{нст}}$ and $I_{\text{юк}}$ can be different, so the frequency in these circuits varies over a wide range, and hence both the pulse width and frequency change here.

PWM - Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) circuits. In these circuits, the duration of pulses at the filter input U_1 remains constant, while their repetition rate is also fixed, and the voltage at the load is inversely proportional to these pulses.

These three methods have advantages and disadvantages that can be compared with each other. In Pulse Width Modulated (PWM) circuits, circuit complexity is high, especially when the voltages $U_{\text{нст}}$ and $U_{\text{юк}}$ vary over a wide range of values. In such cases, it becomes particularly noticeable. These circuits cannot be synchronized using other devices. Therefore, they are not used very often.

DRMs are characterized by large ripples, which is due to their principle of operation. In PWM and PWM schemes, $\Delta U_{\text{юк}}$ can be reduced to zero, but synchronization with other units becomes difficult.

DRM schemes are characterized by relatively large ripples, which is due to the principle of their operation. In PWM and PWM schemes it is possible to minimize ripple $\Delta U_{\text{юк}} = 0$, but synchronization with other blocks becomes more complicated.

PWM schemes are more complex than DRM schemes because they have an additional regulating oscillator.

Advantages of PWM circuits:

- Regardless of changes in the primary voltage sources and load current values, they provide high efficiency and optimal variation frequencies;
- The ripple frequency at the load $R_{\text{юк}}$ remains unchanged, which is important for a number of consumers;

- When several ICNs are operating simultaneously, it is possible to synchronize their frequency changes, which prevents interference (runout). It is also possible to synchronize two devices when operating with an uncontrolled inverter.

Control Element (CE), Lf consider a single-cycle ICN circuit with series connection of the load R_{юк}.

Fig.2-. ICN schematic diagram.

VD2 – Coupling diode;

r_I – resistor that receives the current signal, protecting against short circuits;

VT1 - BE.

This block diagram has a general character (PWM, PWM, URS) and is widely used in practice. Let's consider the principle of its operation. The control transistor VT1 receives a pulse signal from the control circuit.

The pulse rate is changed by means of the signal coming from the feedback circuit, which is connected to the ICN output, i.e. the output voltage and the reference voltage are compared in the control circuit. Choke L_f and capacitor C_f convert the signal coming from the collector of transistor VT1 into a constant voltage with single-phase and rectangular density. Diode VD2 forms a circuit that allows current to flow through the choke when transistor VT1 is closed.

In practice, an additional voltage regulator is often used for the input of converters. Depending on the value of the output power, different types of stabilizers are used. Converters with continuous stabilizers at the input are used when the output power is a few watts and their efficiency factor (efficiency) does not exceed 0.5. In converters with pulsed input stabilizers, the output power can reach several hundred watts. These converters have a higher efficiency of 0.6 to 0.8.

Electronic key is a device designed to switch various circuits of pulse devices under the influence of a control signal. Electronic key circuits are designed to switch the load current. In a stationary state, the key is in one of two states: open or closed.

The following basic requirements are imposed on electronic keys:

1. They should have a small internal resistance in the closed state, and in the open state they should have as large an internal resistance as possible.
2. High speed of operation.
3. High stability of key threshold levels, that is, control signal levels that result in switching.

Depending on the nature of the switched signal, electronic keys (hereinafter - EC) are divided into digital and analog. Digital switches switch the current or voltage of power supplies

and provide two signal levels at the output. One level corresponds to the open state of the key and the second level corresponds to the closed state.

Analog keys are used to open or close analog signal circuits, as well as to transfer analog signals from one circuit of an automatic device to another. Their main parameters are:

1. Sensitivity - is determined by the minimum value of the control signal, upon reaching which the key fully opens or closes;
2. Interference immunity - characterized by the influence of impulse noise on the sensitivity of EC;
3. Voltage drops on the key in the open state and leakage current in the closed state;
4. Resistance of the key in the open and closed states.

Systems that combine groups of keys and auxiliary elements are called switches.

Nowadays, as a rule, contactless elements are used as analog keys, which are highly reliable, fast and consume less power compared to contact keys.

Diodes, bipolar and field-effect transistors are used as proximity switches. They have special control circuits that convert logic signals into current or voltage signals that control the opening or closing of switching elements. Transistor keys are made on bipolar or field-effect transistors. In turn, field-effect transistor keys are subdivided into metal-dielectric-semiconductor (MDS) and field-effect transistor keys with a control p-n junction.

The schemes of electronic keys are diverse. They depend on the type of switching element and the functional purpose of the key. The electronic circuit was assembled in Circuit Design Suite 14 program. This program helps students to understand the principles of electronic circuits and is also used in their design and modeling.

Electronic analog keys are used to connect or disconnect sources of digital and analog information signals. In this case, the characteristics of the measuring instruments used depend on the quality of the signal transmitted through the analog key. In other words, the noise generated during switching of the analog key affects the quality of the analog signal. An electronic key circuit can be viewed as a quadrupole whose parameters change dramatically when the input or control signal reaches a certain level.

When studying the key made on a field-effect transistor (Fig. 1), the following devices are used: a functional generator, which acts as a source of switched signal with internal resistance R_i ; oscilloscope to monitor the signal at the input (channel A) and output (channel B) of the key; voltmeter to measure the signal U_u at the output of the control circuit.

The control circuit is made on the key with bipolar transistor VT2 and a switch. In the circuit shown in Fig. 1, the position of the switch is chosen so that through the resistor R1 to the base of the transistor VT2 is a logical one from the power supply U_{cc} . In this case, the transistor VT2 is open, at its output a low-potential control signal (in millivolts) is formed, which keeps open the main key made on the transistor VT1, which is confirmed by the results of experiments (Fig. 1).

The Multisim 14 electronic systems simulation program simulates the real workplace of a researcher - a laboratory. This virtual laboratory is equipped with real-time measuring instruments.

With Multisim 14 you can design and simulate various simple and complex analog and digital electronic devices. When designing and modeling electronic circuits, this program helps students to better understand the principles of electronic circuits.

Fig-3. Schematic diagram of electronic key on a field-effect transistor

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that the use of Multisim program for research and study of circuits of different complexity awakens students' interest in circuit engineering.

In our opinion, along with the study of electronic circuits on real stands, the assembly and study of these circuits on virtual stands is an important issue in the field of electronics.

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